

HISTORICAL SCIENCES

THE SCIENTIFIC INVESTIGATIONS OF THE OUTSTANDING RESEARCHER SCHOLAR PROFESSOR NISBET MEHDIYEVA IN THE FIELD OF CULTURE (60 – 80s of the XX century)

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ABSTRACT

A person is always distinguished, formed and differs from other individuals active in society by their talent, broad worldview, skills and abilities, great hard work, endless trust, and the persistent just struggle they conduct. This uniqueness is such a characteristic feature that it is impossible to hide or cover it up. The individuals with such uniqueness, despite all the difficulties, injustice and lawlessness they encountered in society, have succeeded in overcoming all these difficulties and obstacles by following their own path, have always spoken their mind, voiced their thoughts and ideas, and progressive positions, and have always tirelessly fought against the negative elements of society and the shortcomings caused by the various objective and subjective situations. When such uniqueness appears in science, these individuals become the outstanding researchers, great scientists, creative intellectuals with infinite abilities – progressive intelligentsia. The scientific investigations conducted by such researcher scholars always means the innovation, progress, constant development of this field of science, great scientific creativity, hard work, the creation, elaboration and publication of valuable scientific research works that are accurate and refer only to real facts. Such talented individuals who speak their own words in science and follow their own path constantly develop science, enrich it and always work on themselves. The researcher scholar should be distinguished, differed and matured in science not only by his talent, skills and abilities, and uniqueness, but also by his hard work, constant diligence, scientific investigations he conducts, problematic issues he raises, fundamental scientific fields he works and researches, rich sources he raises, etc. The researchers conduct the investigations in various scientific fields, develop science, and become familiar with all the subtleties of science through the works they write. The science of history is no exception in this regard. The prominent historians ensure the continuous development of this field of science with their valuable works. In this regard, Professor Nisbet Mehdiyeva, the natural talent, the wonderful historian, the valuable researcher, always distinguished and working only with her talent, endless skills and abilities, has dedicated the extremely valuable and fundamental research works to the period of Azerbaijan culture from the 60s to the 80s of the XX century. The intense scientific investigations conducted by Professor Nisbet Mehdiyeva in the field of culture is a clear example of the great hard work of the scientist over many years, her tireless scientific activity, great talent, scientific sense, all the positive qualities of a true researcher, broad outlook, research experience, scientific skill, progressive thoughts and ideas. Each of these researches, being an invaluable fundamental work, a valuable scientific source, and the result of intense and great effort, is the logical result of the scholar's enormous scientific activity in the field of the development of culture and holds considerable significance.

Keywords: scientist, researcher, uniqueness, progressive thoughts and ideas, Azerbaijan, culture, spheres, scientific investigations.

Introduction

Azerbaijan is beautiful with its history, culture, science, art, valuable people with inexhaustible human qualities, its fighting and fair sons and daughters who always paving their own way with their natural talent, skills and abilities, great hard work, scientific sense and skill, who speak only their own words and follow their own path, who work with true intellectual conscience and responsibility. Such people always differ from others with their high moral qualities and stand above everything. The individuals with such values, walking through the complex, difficult, and impassable paths of science, become more mature and excellent scientists with the broader worldview, progressive thoughts and ideas. They say it rightly: "It is easy to be a scientist, it is difficult to be a human being". However, it is very difficult to be both a scientist and a mature person. The twists and turns of life, difficulties and shortcomings, positive and negative manifestations of everyday life,

the methods and means of objective and subjective influence of the environment on society and individuals, the conscious and superficial attitude towards everything and humanity, the attitude of society and specific individuals towards the events, injustice and lawlessness in the environment, etc. elements are analyzed, studied, investigated, the problematic issues are raised and researched, their causes, the reasons that give rise to them, the unresolved and unstudied aspects facing this sphere of science are involved in research and find their scientific solution. As a result of intensive researches, true research scholars – professional intellectuals are formed, capable of conquering the highest peaks of science, studying and developing the specific field of science they work in with precision and responsibility. The professional researcher scholars are characterized by their own set – lines, creative styles, realistic views of life and science, forms of approach to a specific field of science, uniqueness, etc. qualities. The

professional researcher scholars, who enrich the specific field of science they study with their characteristic features, progressive thoughts and ideas, and the various research methods and forms, combine all of these ones together to achieve the advancement of unified scientific concepts and develop the spheres of their research guided by them. The researcher scholar brings his progressive thoughts and ideas to that field of science, involves it in comprehensive research, seeks, finds, and investigates solutions to the problem by referring to the various sources, and turns these studies into excellent scientific works and fundamental creative products. These research works, based on the most mature, creative, progressive and realistic thoughts and ideas of professional researchers, emerge as the real result of the hard work, great scientific researches and beautiful scholarly pen of prominent scientists who specialize in these fields and become the professional researchers. The activity and creativity of such researchers undoubtedly deserve the great respect and love. The outstanding historian, renowned researcher, true intellectual, the scientist with natural talent, extraordinary skills and abilities, the professional historian – cultural scholar, Doctor of Historical Sciences, Professor Nisbet Mehdiyeva as an excellent historian scholar can be considered the most prominent scientist who has made her original mark not only in the development of historical science, but also in the field of development, research and purely scientific study of culture. Professor Nisbet Mehdiyeva, who deeply studied the period of Azerbaijan culture from the 60s to the 80s of the 20th century and dedicated the fundamental scientific works to various spheres of culture, raised the various problematic issues with her scientific research works, investigated them, and conducted the extensive scientific investigations. Professor Nisbet Mehdiyeva's scientific investigations covers almost all areas of culture and is quite remarkable in this respect.

1. The work done in the field of culture in Azerbaijan in the 60 – 80s of the XX century

Each period has its own objective and subjective conditions. These conditions have an impact on the development and formation of society, and its gradual departure from the template positions and lifestyle, its progressive, innovative, transparent and correct path, and its taking a fair development course. The most important requirement of the period should be to raise the state and the people, including the intellectuals, who are considered the true inexhaustible value of the people, to the politically, economically and culturally conscious and mature level, and to mobilize the scientific and creative potential of the intellectuals in the most efficient and humane way for this. From this point of view, the 60 – 80s of the XX century should be considered one of the most productive, mature in terms of the development of ideological – political thought, the most humane in terms of humanity, and the most progressive and advanced in terms of culture in the history of Azerbaijan.

Every nation is formed and develops with its own culture, and in this process, getting rid of all shortcomings, it constantly tries to educate the most valuable qualities in itself, respect for people, great esteem and

care for parents, protection of true intellectuals, development of the homeland in the right direction, avoiding wrong words and actions, respecting other people and not interfering in their lives, always reading, working, fighting against injustice, making friends with science and books, removing oppression and torture from the life of society, being ideologically and politically mature, approaching the right and wrong events taking place in the world and the country only from an objective and scientific prism, resisting the unacceptable behavior of ignorant people with true intellectuals, loving the world and the country, protecting its material and spiritual wealth, taking ownership of them, fighting against and overcoming all obstacles and difficulties that always arise on the way to preserving and protecting the rich moral values of the people, building our world on correct values, etc. The leading role in all this moral, aesthetic and spiritual development belongs to culture.

The culture is perfect and beautiful in all its spheres. This beauty is manifested in the education, science, art, behavior, daily life of the people, people's attitudes, perception of the world, understanding of the environment, the influence of the beauties of nature into human life and livelihood, etc. episodes. For the creation of this beauty and outstanding cultural achievements, the intellectuals working in the field of culture, the various organizations and institutions were constantly working, laboring and engaged in the necessary activity. In this regard, the activity of the Azerbaijan Creative Unions and the creative intellectuals represented in their ranks was especially noteworthy in the 60 – 80s of the XX century.

The development of culture is closely connected in the study and understanding of areas that are considered an inexhaustible treasure of national culture – architecture, music, visual arts, decorative – applied arts, etc. [28, 3]. The development of various types of painting, architecture, visual arts, decorative – applied arts, music, theater and cinema had a complex and multifaceted palette in the 1960 and 1970s. This period of Azerbaijan culture was characterized by the diversity of creative forms and methods, their unique features and different style trends [28, 4]. During this period, the intensive development of all areas of culture led to the emergence and development of a new field in science – architecture and art history. The art historians were engaged in the collection and study of musical folklore samples, the development problems of Azerbaijan music of this period, the issues of history and modern development of theatrical art, etc. aspects. In the 60s of the XX century, a number of research works were written and published – “Monumental Sculpture of Soviet Azerbaijan” (1960), “Architectural Ornament of Azerbaijan” (1961), “Soviet Graphics of Azerbaijan” (1962), “History of Azerbaijan Architecture” (1963), “Azerbaijan Folk Architecture and Its Progressive Traditions” (1963) and “Art Ceramics of Azerbaijan” (1964) [28, 5, 6]. Already in the late 60s and early 70s of the XX century, certain research works were carried out in the field of studying the history and modern trends of visual arts. As a result, the research works dedicated to this field were published – “Visual Arts of Soviet Azerbaijan” (1970), “Architecture of Soviet

Azerbaijan" (1973), "Azim Azimzade's creativity and his place in the development of Azerbaijan Soviet graphics" (1976), "Azerbaijan decorative – applied art" (1976), "Sculpture of Soviet Azerbaijan" (1979), etc. [28, 7].

In the field of music, the valuable research works have been created and published, dedicated to the Azerbaijan folk music and professional musical creativity, activity of prominent composers, modern trends of this period, creative problems, collection, classification and study of national musical folklore, scientific analysis, study and publication of Azerbaijan mughams, ashug creativity, dance music, folk songs, folk musical instruments, creation of a musical – ethnographic atlas of Azerbaijan and etc., on actual issues. Among them it is possible to give an example as "Camera – instrumental creativity of Azerbaijan Soviet composers" (1961), Azerbaijan mughams "Chargah and Humayun" (1962), "Rast and Shahnaz" and "Bayati – Shiraz and Shur" (1963), "Chargah" (1970), also "Establishment and development of Azerbaijan musical theater" (1968) and etc. [28, 8].

The researches conducted by the theater scholars in the field of studying Azerbaijan Theater were devoted to the current problems facing the theater, the establishment of communication between the theater and the audience, the adaptation of theater repertoires to the modern era and reality, the development of acting, the establishment of the actor, director and audience perspective, the staging of works of art that concern and make different segments of society think, the selection and formation of a skilled acting team, the involvement of professional personnel in performances and theaters, etc. issues. The examples of these research works include "Azerbaijan Dramatic Theater" (1962), "Akhundov and Theater" (1962), "Youth Theater of Soviet Azerbaijan" (1969), "Azerbaijan Theater for 100 Years" (1974), etc. [28, 9].

The various research works of film scholars dedicated to the modern trends of Azerbaijan cinema, have reflected the history and development of cinema, the training of film actors, the writing of scripts for films, the formation of the audience, the writing and analysis of film literature, the preparation of film playwrights, the modern state of film works, the training of professional film actors, issues of film creativity, the formation of fields such as film studies and film criticism, the dedication of feature and documentary films to actual issues, the formation of the plot line in feature films based on the artistic imagination and real facts, the response of the problems raised in films to the spiritual needs of all strata of society, etc. necessary aspects. In 1971, the book "Azerbaijan Documentary" was dedicated to the history of the creation, formation and development of documentary films [28, 9].

The literature has undergone a great and fruitful development in the 60 – 80s of the XX century. The literature has achieved the significant successes in understanding the multifaceted development trends of modern reality, developing traditions of artistic creativity, overcoming genre – style and idea – thematic limitations, introducing progressive thoughts and ideas into fiction, proportional and regular development of the

writer's imagination and real – life events, idea – thematic diversity, richness of genre and artistic style directions, development of unique forms and methods [8, 25]. The development of Azerbaijan prose in the 60s of the XX century was directly connected in the documentary – fiction genre. The plot of the events described in the work was taken from real life, the reflection of human characters typical of the best literary works, etc. characteristic features were actual for Azerbaijan prose of this period [8, 32]. The role of the paces of development of modern Azerbaijan poetry, the enthusiasm for poetic creativity and etc. in the intensive creative search for the diversity of genres and styles, the discovery of new poetic forms and means, the demonstration of a civic position, the imagery of poetic thought, maturity and perfection of artistic form, etc. characteristic features were typical for this period [8, 34]. Along with Azerbaijan poetry and prose, it would be appropriate to specially note the real spectrum of activity of Azerbaijan dramaturgy during this period. The Azerbaijan dramaturgy during this period was quite relevant due to its ideological – thematic and genre diversity. The written plays were mostly devoted to historical, moral – ethical, positive and negative features of society, commentary aspects of the issue from the moral – philosophical and moral perspective [8, 39, 40].

It is necessary to note the role of the socio – political and creative – organizational works carried out by the Azerbaijan Writers' Union in the field of development of Azerbaijan literature. The Azerbaijan Writers' Union held 10 plenums between the V and VI congresses [14, 7]. In 1972, the plenum was held on the topic "Criticism, Literature and Modernity" dedicated to the state and tasks of modern literary criticism [14, 8]. In 1973, the plenum dedicated to the issue of "Song genre, its development and promotion" was held under the joint organization of the Azerbaijan Writers' Union, the Composers' Union and the Ministry of Culture. Here, it was considered appropriate to establish a special song section in the Azerbaijan Composers' Union for the development and promotion of the song genre [14, 9 – 10, 11]. In 1974, the Writers' Union held the mobile plenum on the topic "The Writer and Life". In 1973, the Azerbaijan Writers' Union together with the Union of Journalists, held the plenum dedicated to the issues of publicism. Here, the important socio – political meaning of publicism in the modern period and the main issues facing it were discussed [14, 11 – 12].

During this period, the Writers' Union began to realize the creative – organizational measures for the effective implementation of the work of its creative departments. The Writers' Union's Criticism Department, Children's Literature Department, Translation Department, Prose and Poetry Department, Drama Department and etc. structural creative departments were effectively operating in the field of development of various spheres [14, 13 – 14]. In 1975, the issue of improving the situation of fiction translation in the republic was raised before the press agencies, publishing houses and the literary departments of the radio and television committee [14, 14]. The Union has implemented the various practical measures in the press organs of the Writers' Union – the "Literature and Art" newspaper, the "Ulduz" magazine, the "Azerbaijan"

and "Literary Azerbaijan" magazines related to the state of literary criticism, the publication of more critical articles, the raising of actual problems, etc. aspects [14, 14 – 15]. The Azerbaijan Writers' Union Bureau for the Promotion of Fiction played the decisive role in carrying out mass cultural education work [14, 21]. Between 1970 and 1975, the writers held 27.563 meetings. About 200 writers participated in these meetings [14, 21, 22]. The Bureau actively participated in the organization of children's and youth book weeks every year, also reader conferences, book discussions held in cultural – educational institutions and other events [14, 22]. The Azerbaijan Writers' Union was engaged in important social – political and creative – organizational activities participating in the spiritual and aesthetic education of the people to form them in the spirit of progressive ideas, on the basis of mature spiritual and moral values, and in the light of democratic principles based only on real facts.

The Azerbaijan musical art is rich in its large – scale and diverse achievements. Its main target was to raise Azerbaijan music to a worthy stage of development of world musical culture, at the same time to preserve its uniqueness, to create specific examples of art that meet the requirements of the period and progressive in form and essence, and to enrich it with new innovative thoughts and ideas. In the 60s and 70s of the XX century, the Azerbaijan music was enriched with the best examples of modern musical culture. The musical art of this period was characterized by the diversity of artistic manifestations, the complexity of various means of expression, which brought the radical changes to the traditional musical language [1, 74].

In the 60s of the XX century, the ballet music creativity written on different subjects began to gain wide popularity. The beautiful performance, excellent composer's work, unique productions given to ballet performances turned the mysterious ballet music into a pearl of art. During this period, along with unique ballet music, choreographic miniatures and ballet – novella music were also written [2, 54; 1, 75]. During this period, new operas were written. In 1963, the first children's opera ballet was staged in the republic. Although these works enriched the theatrical life of the country, the development of the opera genre was not as intensive and effective as the ballet genre. During this period, the list of musical comedy works continued to increase. The innovative tendencies were manifested in the field of symphonic music creativity. The music was composed for chamber orchestras [2, 55; 1, 75]. The field of chamber instrumental creativity was gradually expanding, the organ music was being written. During this period, the importance of the cantata – oratorio genre in Azerbaijan music increased. The development of these areas of musical art meant that new ideas were introduced into musical creativity, innovative directions gained momentum, traditional Azerbaijan music was combined with the professional creativity, and as a result, excellent examples of art were created. The field of song creativity was also constantly developing, and the prominent composers of the country worked in this sphere [2, 55]. The 60 – 80s of the XX century were marked by the rapid development of opera creativity

and the emergence of new works in this field. The everyday motifs, themes of ancient legends and myths, and children's tales were used in these works. Some composers widely used the mugham elements and the folk art in writing operas. The introduction of musical folklore into the professional music could be considered a very progressive trend [2, 56]. During this period, the Azerbaijan composers successfully worked in all areas of musical art. The professional music creativity was dynamically developing in the fields of ballet, vocal – choreographic poetry, musical comedy, opera, operetta, vocal – symphonic, chamber – instrumental, etc. [2, 57, 58].

In the 60 – 80s of the XX century, the field of Azerbaijan musicology was notable for the writing of valuable research works dedicated to almost all prominent composers of the country, popular brochures, the scientific essays on the development directions of Azerbaijan music, and the evolution of various genres in the creativity of composers [2, 58 – 59].

The IV and V congresses of the Azerbaijan Composers' Union (1973 and 1979), dedicated to the final reports and prospects of the development of musical art in the republic, discussed the current progress, achievements and successes in this field, and determined a course of action for taking practical measures, taking into account all the obstacles and difficulties that faced [1, 80].

The Azerbaijan painting, as one of the leading areas of visual arts, is characterized by the diversity of themes and genres, the hard work and activity of talented creative individuals. Guided by the creative experience of outstanding artists, it is necessary to note the main trends of Azerbaijan painting – the emotional and figurative meaning of the subject, the search for bright visual decorative forms, the great interest in the national artistic heritage, the introduction of innovative and progressive ideas into art, etc. [13, 84]. The artists working in the genres of thematic paintings, portraits and landscapes created the beautiful examples of art with their fine brushes, evaluating the heroes of their works through the prism of actual issues of the period, the theme of the homeland, the depictions of people from the various fields of art who were their contemporaries, the prominent figures, the historical figures, the natural landscapes, the plots dedicated to human destiny and other remarkable events. One of the main qualities of Azerbaijan painting during this period was the diversity of personal characteristics. In the 60 – 80s of the XX century, the Azerbaijan artists worked in the leading fields of graphics, autolithography, linocut, color and black – and – white engraving, book graphics, mass forms of graphics – posters and caricatures, illustrations drawn for fiction works, etc. The examples of caricatures drawn in the field of satirical graphics stood out among other genres of modern graphics and gradually took their rightful place [13, 92, 93, 94]. During this period, the certain progress was achieved in the fields of monumental – decorative and theatrical – decoration creativity. The professional theatrical and film painters, masters of monumental – decorative art were formed in the republic. The Azerbaijan painters, their graphics, book illustrations and posters were known in

various places, including European countries. The various industrial enterprises, cultural palaces, hotels and other public and catering facilities were decorated with monumental works created by talented artists [13, 94]. During this period, the numerous exhibitions were organized in Baku and other cities of the republic, the special attention was paid to the design of stage for theatrical performances and films, which were distinguished by their greater mass nature of creativity, the creation of decorative – applied art examples, the synthesis of architecture with the various fields of art, etc. The audience flow to the various museum expositions and art exhibitions was gradually increasing. The visual arts played a decisive role in the spiritual, ideological – aesthetic formation of people. The Azerbaijan art is extensively exhibited in numerous thematic, mobile, personal and international exhibitions, is written about in the press and audiences expressed their opinions [9, 32]. The Azerbaijan art of painting in this period, which reflected the complicated events of the historical past, the people's everyday concerns and problems, the images of their contemporaries, the natural landscapes of the homeland and other actual aspects, adorned the expositions of all exhibitions, galleries and museums of Baku with its beautiful examples of art [9, 34, 36].

During this period, the field of sculpture was also developing dynamically. The Azerbaijan sculptors were productive in the fields of monumental, compositional, portrait, decorative and memorial sculpture. They prepared their works in the synthesis of various arts, creating colorful sculptural compositions, reliefs and examples of art using the minting method. The main creative trends characteristic for painting and sculpture in the 60 and 70s of the XX century were connection with real events, manifestation of civic position, diversity and innovation of means of depiction, gradual restoration of the dynamics of development of some graphic genres, development of political posters and book illustrations, improvement of the quality of artistic design of printed products, artistic design and illustration of classical and modern literary examples occupied the important place in this regard [9, 36, 38]. The painters who provided the artistic design for the dramatic and musical performances staged in the Academic Drama Theater and the Academic Opera and Ballet Theater played the important role in the development of Azerbaijan theatrical art [9, 40]. Already in the 70s of the XX century, the ideological – thematic level of works created in the field of painting gradually strengthened, and the professional approach came to the fore. New compositions, portraits, landscapes, graphic works, posters of various kinds, etc. began to appear. The various palaces of culture, public buildings and cultural – educational institutions were decorated with the colorful mosaics, paintings and frescoes. The innovative young painters also closely participated in this process. By this time, more than 400 painters, graphic artists, sculptors, masters of applied and theatrical – decoration arts – professional painters – were already working at the Azerbaijan Artists' Union. Baku had become a beautiful city with its own palaces of culture, art galleries, exhibition halls, museums, and unique examples of sculpture. All this was possible as a result of the great work and practical activity of the

creative intellectuals working in the field of visual arts [9, 42, 43].

The Azerbaijan theater has passed the great and glorious path of development. It has actively participated in the formation and development of progressive public opinion in the republic. The theater has enriched the spiritual treasure of the people, brought the vital problems to the stage and presented them to the people with realistic features, and has been closely connected with the national intelligentsia and the people of country [5, 62]. The theater figures, with their invaluable services to art, have not only been able to significantly develop the theater art, but have also succeeded in making their own contributions to universal culture. Azerbaijan theater is also the real embodiment of Azerbaijan history [6, 92]. In the early 60s of the XX century, the various new works were staged. In addition to staging the original works of Azerbaijan playwrights, the certain steps were also taken in the field of staging the best examples of the translated literature [6, 97]. During this period, the young and talented actors who appeared on the theater stages working shoulder to shoulder with the representatives of the older and middle generation, participated in the theater performances that corresponded to high artistic – aesthetic taste [5, 71]. The Azerbaijan National Drama Theater, which has undergone the complex path of formation and development, has fought for realistic art throughout its whole activity. Constantly working on this path, the Azerbaijan theater has become quite artistically mature and has played the decisive role in the ideological – aesthetic education of the people [5, 74]. The Azerbaijan theater has trained its own original national personnel, talented directors and theater figures. The performances staged by these directors have always been distinguished for their uniqueness and formed the Azerbaijan theater's own development path [6, 103]. In 1971, the Actor's House named after A.M.Sharifzadeh was opened in Baku. The events held here played the important role in the development and promotion of theatrical art [10, 7]. The Azerbaijan Theater Society organized the various events at the Actor's House under the mottos of "Young Actor and Theater", "Composer and Theater", "Stage Masters on the Screen", "Playwright and Theater", International Theater Day, etc. [10, 7]. The Actor's House held also the events from the series of "Azerbaijan Stage Masters on Screen" and "Theater, Music and Poetry". Here, actors, directors, ballet masters, composers, poets, writers, theater and film figures gave the reports on their creativity, the films were screened, and the scenes from their performances were shown [20, 16, 18; 1, 15].

The Creative Unions of Republic were constantly searching for new forms and means to increase the artistic – aesthetic and educational significance of works. Such forms of events include discussions of fiction works, reader and audience conferences, establishing relations between the audience and the actor – director, creative reports and discussions, exchanges of ideas, audience opinions and other aspects [10, 18]. The form and scope of the reader' conferences were quite diverse. The activity of the Azerbaijan Theater Society in this field attracted attention. In 1960, the Azerbaijan Theater Society carried out the practical activity to regularly

convene reader` conferences every year and hold creative debates after the performances. The target was to familiarize each viewer with the work and its performers [17; 10, 19]. The audience conferences held by the Azerbaijan Theater Society also had a very wide scope of influence [10, 20]. In 1971, the Azerbaijan Theater Society, effectively using the lecture – propaganda method, organized during 6 years 596 lectures on the problems of theater art in various parts of the republic. The examples of these include “Realism in Theater”, “Modern Reading of Classics”, etc. The lectures were aimed at familiarizing the audience with the problems of theater art, repertoire, issues of craftsmanship, etc. aspects [10, 25]. The Azerbaijan Theater Society regularly promoted the works of art by holding the theater weeks [10, 34]. In 1971, the Azerbaijan Theater Society, together with the House of Folk Creativity, held the “Week of Folk Theaters”. Such events played the important role in the emergence of folk talents and the development of folk theaters [19; 10, 34]. As a result of about 20 views of folk theaters organized in 1963, it became clear that there were the talented collectives and creative, capable individuals among them. Therefore, the permanent commission was created in the Theater Society of the Republic to assist folk theaters [10, 50]. The Theater Society held the talks and lectures on creativity with the folk theaters, and published relevant literature for them. The creative – methodological council operated under the Ministry of Culture of Azerbaijan to assist the folk theaters [22, 15; 10, 50]. The artists from some theaters of the republic led the folk theaters [10, 50]. The certain measures were taken in the field of promotion of the theatrical art. In the field of dramaturgy and theatrical art, relatively little space was allocated to the works that were “Literary events”, global topics, actual plays and performances, and important events of different periods. The organization of festivals that meet modern requirements, the regulation of the activity of theatrical troupes, etc. can be considered among the tasks facing us during this period [10, 77]. In 1986, the II Republican Festival of Folk Creativity was held. Within the framework of the festival, views, competitions were organized, performances were shown in the cities and regions of the republic. This view differed from previous festivals in its scale and tasks. For the first time, the view of the plays and performances of drama collectives was held by zones according to the program of the Festival of Folk Creativity. The professional directors, actors and theater critics watched the performances of more than 100 collectives – 48 folk theaters, 35 drama clubs and 20 propaganda brigades [10, 79].

In order to strengthen the enthusiasm and interest in the theatrical performances, it was extremely necessary to constantly update the repertoires of theaters, improve the acting and directing work, attract professional specialists to theaters, and consistently organize theater tours. In the 60s and 70s of the XX century, the performances based on the various works of foreign and domestic authors occupied the important place in the repertoire of theaters of the republic. Thus, the various operas and ballets were staged at the Azerbaijan State Academic Opera and Ballet Theater [23, 85; 10, 81], the performances based on the works of modern and

classical authors at the Azerbaijan State Academic Drama Theater [24, 88 – 90; 10, 81], the works of professional and young authors reflecting the various actual issues were performed on the stage of folk theaters [21, 9; 10, 81]. The performances in the repertoire of Azerbaijan theaters were played in the various parts of the republic by both professional theaters and folk theaters [10, 81]. In 1966 – 1967, all the theaters of the republic showed 8015 performances. Of these, 100 performances were in new productions [25, 32; 10, 83]. The theater is a complex creative field. The creative organizations, theater collectives, playwrights, and theater critics worked together here [10, 83]. The Azerbaijan Theater Society organized the meetings, lectures, creative evenings, photo exhibitions, photo stands, etc. connected in the various literary – artistic and historical events in order to increase the relevance and strengthen the propaganda of the theatrical art [23, 85; 10, 84]. In the early 80s of the XX century, 14 state and 41 folk theaters operated in Azerbaijan. In 1980, 849 performances were shown in the republic’s theaters and the number of spectators reached 195 thousand [7, 172; 10, 84 – 85]. The Azerbaijan theater has always played the active role in the formation of high moral and spiritual qualities of the people and in the cultural education. The theater enriched the spiritual world of society and improved its aesthetic taste. In this regard, its role is irreplaceable.

At a time when there was still a shortage of specialists – national personnel – in the field of cinema, the Azerbaijan Drama Theater succeeded in preparing a generation of outstanding artists. The activity of these personnel in the field of cinema led to the development of Azerbaijan cinema and the creation of unique works of art [4, 105]. Already in the 60 – 80s of the XX century, the Azerbaijan cinema achieved the remarkable successes in the form of beautiful movies, filming the most important and significant events of the people and the country in a very short period of time [3, 96]. In the 60s of the XX century, the colorful films were shot based on the materials reflecting the various aspects of the life of the republic. Among these, the films for children and youth played the important role in the enrichment of national cinema and the development of the creativity of film figures. In the early 60s, the first color films began to be produced in Azerbaijan. Later, the widescreen color films in the musical comedy genre were also shot [4, 114]. In 1964, the genre of the Cinema Almanac was first used. The almanacs shot on the base of short stories on the various topics were often dedicated to some types of sport. Thus, in 1966, at the First All – Union Sports Films Festival, the short story “The Force of Attraction” took the special place among Azerbaijan films, including film almanacs, for its poetic depiction of the theme of sports, and gained the sympathy of the audience. In 1966, the second film almanac consisting of 2 short stories was shot. This film almanac was also met with great interest due to its different plot, excellent directorial work and skillful acting, and has become a source of admiration for the film community and the audience [4, 116, 118]. The arrival of new specialists – directors and screenwriters – to Azerbaijan cinema in the late 1960s led to the development of this field and the creation of interesting films.

The number of films shot during this period increased, the young directors along with the professional directors, also participated in them and managed to reveal their talents [4, 120]. In 1974, a new film almanac was shot at the “Azerbaijanfilm” studio based on several short stories. These short stories reflected the various topics, including moral – ethical problems that have always made people think [4, 122]. Like feature films, documentary filmmaking has also undergone a glorious development and formation in Azerbaijan. Already in the 60 – 80s of the XX century, the documentary films were shot, the diversity of the subjects and the form of factual analysis achieved the noticeable successes. The professional steps were being taken in this field, and the film figures involved in the shooting of documentary films were gradually becoming more mature, were known in the country and abroad [4, 123].

The “Azerbaijanfilm” studio published the magazines “Soviet Azerbaijan” and “Young Generation”, as well as the satirical magazine “Mozalan”. During this period, the achievements of the republic in the various fields were reflected in documentary films on different topics made by the country’s creative intellectuals – documentary filmmakers – directors – “The Truth About My Republic”, “Our Azerbaijan”, etc. These films also demonstrated the interesting and real facts about the republic’s political, economic and cultural relations with foreign countries [4, 124]. It should be noted that the urgent problems of modern life have always been in the focus of attention of Azerbaijan filmmakers. The protection of true spiritual – moral values, the complex process of formation of ethical norms, the constant struggle against the difficulties, problems and shortcomings faced by society and the people formed the main plot line of all films shot in these years. The cinematographers, correctly understanding the role and function of cinema in this work, have an irreplaceable position in the process of cultural education, primarily through their art and practical activity [3, 103 – 104].

The Union of Cinematographers of Azerbaijan was engaged in the development of cinema in the republic. This creative union included film playwrights, film directors, film operators, actors, film critics, editors, composers, artists, sound operators and film workers. In 1975, the Union of Cinematographers of Azerbaijan had 137 members [26, 1]. The Union of Cinematographers had the film dramaturgy department, the feature film department, the documentary film department, the film criticism department, the film lovers department, the television department and the cartoon (animation) department [26, 3]. In 1970, at the joint meeting of the Republic’s Creative Unions, the development of Azerbaijan cinema, the issues facing it, achievements and shortcomings were discussed [26, 5 – 6]. In October 1971, the plenum of the Union of Cinematographers of Azerbaijan entitled “Problems of Cinematographers of the Republic and Tasks in the Modern Period” was dedicated to the tasks of documentary filmmakers [26, 6]. In 1972, the Union of Cinematographers of Azerbaijan participated in the joint plenum of the republic’s creative unions. In December 1973, at the next plenum entitled “Problems of Azerbaijan Television Films”, the report of the scenario –

editorial board of the “Azerbaijanfilm” creative union analyzed the current state of Azerbaijan television film, revealed its professional and creative opportunities, and voiced its important and urgent problems [26, 8, 9]. During this period, the issues facing the Union of Cinematographers of Azerbaijan included: granting creative trips, receiving foreign guests, discussing lectures and reports, establishing a new cinema – the Cinema Lecture House, the activity of the Cinema House, organizing the work of creative departments, holding film festivals, accepting talented and creative individuals to the members of the Union of Cinematographers, etc. [26, 12]. The main creative activity of the Azerbaijan Cinematographers Union consisted of the holding creative meetings, discussions and round tables with film directors, creative teams, filming crews, film playwrights, film enthusiasts, creative teams of documentary films, the giving lectures dedicated to the problems of cinema and film creativity, the organizing screenings and premieres of feature films, documentaries and animated films produced by the “Azerbaijanfilm” studio, the holding conferences and theoretical conferences, the establishing relations between the film critics and newspapers editorial offices, the organizing creative conferences on film criticism, etc. At the same time, the newly released issues of the satirical film magazine “Mozalan” were being discussed and reviewed. The Union of Cinematographers of Azerbaijan, together with the Azerbaijan State Committee for Cinematography and the Film Distribution Office of the Republic, held discussions on the issues of the information – advertising bulletin “New Films”. Most of these events were being organized and held by the relevant creative departments of the Azerbaijan Cinematographers Union. The Union paid attention to the writing, discussion and compliance of scripts with the requirements of the modern period. Every month, the program “Writer and Screen” was broadcast on television. It touched on topical issues such as the screening of literary works, the multifaceted relationship between literature and cinema, etc. [26, 12 – 18]. The Azerbaijan cinematographers made speeches, gave reports and lectures at events on the modern trends of our cinema, the tasks facing film dramaturgy in the production of films dedicated to current issues and themes of the modern period, etc., exchanged ideas, and participated in theoretical and creative conferences. The young and talented personnel were also being involved in this work.

The main form of activity of the Cinema House was regular informational screenings of new films. The creative departments of the Azerbaijan Cinematographers Union organized their activity in the Cinema House, where premieres and discussions of new films of the “Azerbaijanfilm” studio and the “Azerbaijanfilm” creative association were being held [26, 21]. The lecturers who came to the Cinema House with programs of foreign films gave a series of lectures on modern trends in American, English, French and Italian cinema. The Discussion Film Club also operated here. Once a month, the Cinema House held a joint event with the Actors’ House. Here, the film critics gave lectures on progressive film masters and the best achievements of world cinema. The Cinema House also hosted screenings of Azerbaijan feature and documentary

films for foreign guests. The purpose of these screenings was to familiarize the guests with the state of cinematography in the republic, its development, achievements and shortcomings. The Azerbaijan Cinematographers Union actively participated in the development of cinematography in the republic and constantly fought for the prosperity and success of cinematography [26, 22].

2. The scientific investigations conducted by Professor Nisbet Mehdiyeva in the field of culture and their impact on the development of Azerbaijan culture

The culture, which is formed and operates at the intersection of various fields, has developed, enriched, and reached the perfect level of modernity, progress, innovation, and adherence to almost all positive traditions passing through all the hardships of the period, thanks to the great effort, talent, and unparalleled bravery of the most beautiful, capable, talented, hardworking, and heroic persons of each nation, its mature and conscious representatives, and its great intellectuals who have faced and overcome the most difficult and complex obstacles of the time.

A human is the person who creates, forms science, and elevates knowledge to the level of science. The culture is a delicate, precisely contoured, highly pompous, at the same time charming, rhythmic, playful, cheerful melody, colorful shades, monumental appearance, beautiful ornamentation, sharp and complex character, skillful acting and performing ability, incomparable erudite, etc., with superior and unreplaceable qualities, each of which is a separate independent field of science, and at the same time, is a perfect manifestation of independent fields of science together, a single whole. The independent fields of science that form the culture have developed both separately, independently, and in the context of general culture as inseparable components of culture. Such a multifaceted development process of culture has always been in the focus of researchers. The field of culture, each sphere of which is separately involved in research, requires from each researcher to be prepared, familiar with rare artistic pearls of world culture, as well as to be familiar with classical and modern examples of the culture of the country that is the object of investigation, to know the work done in this field, to take into consideration the characteristic features of the field that is the object of study, the uniqueness of the research process, etc. objective and subjective conditions, to be realistic, to act from a fair position, to remain faithful to the ideas of realism, to put the name of

each thing and event on oneself, great effort, talent, skills and abilities. Although different researchers have studied this field at different times, only a few truly research scientists have succeeded in understanding the essence of this sphere, engaging it in true scientific research, conducting intense scientific investigations in this field day and night, creating valuable scientific works, examining every field of culture carefully, humbly, with the precision and skill of a true scientist, and speaking their minds as scientists working in this field and researching it.

The wonderful researcher, the true scientist, the beloved teacher, the beautiful and dear mother, Doctor of Historical Sciences, Professor Nisbet Mehdiyeva can be considered one of the few scientists who has spoken her scholarly word in the field of the investigation of culture, has studied this field for many years, carefully researched each of its spheres, and involved it in scientific research. Professor Nisbet Mehdiyeva is at the forefront of the republic as the author of the fundamental scientific works in the field of research of culture. In 1990, Professor Nisbet Mehdiyeva wrote and published the textbook entitled "The activity of the Azerbaijan Creative Unions in the field of mass propaganda (1960 – 1980s)". Professor Nisbet Mehdiyeva's monograph "The cultural relations of the Azerbaijan Creative Unions (1960 – 1980s)" was published in 1991. The distinguished researcher defended her doctoral dissertation "The activity of the Azerbaijan Creative Unions in the field of the development of culture (1960 – 1980s)" in 1991. Professor Nisbet Mehdiyeva is the author of 2 monographs and 5 textbooks. The researcher scholar wrote and published her first monograph in 1991, and her second monograph in 2014. In 2014, Professor Nisbet Mehdiyeva's monograph "The activity of the Azerbaijan Creative Unions in the field of the development of culture (1960 – 1980s)" was published. In 1990, 1991 and 2014, Professor Nisbet Mehdiyeva wrote and published 1 textbook, 2 monographs and numerous scientific articles dedicated to the activity of the Azerbaijan Creative Unions in the field of the development of culture in the republic in the 1960 – 1980s. In 1991, the researcher scholar Professor Nisbet Mehdiyeva defended her doctoral dissertation on the activity of the Azerbaijan Creative Unions in the field of the development of culture in the period 1960 – 1980s, and was recognized as the most prominent researcher scientist working in this field in the republic.

Image 1. Doctor of Historical Sciences, Professor Nisbet Mehdiyeva and her textbook “The activity of the Azerbaijan Creative Unions in the field of mass propaganda (1960 – 1980s)” (1990)

The researcher scientist Professor Nisbet Mehdiyeva in her 1990 textbook “The activity of the Azerbaijan Creative Unions in the field of mass propaganda (1960 – 1980s)” examined in detail the mass propaganda activity carried out by these organizations in the field of widespread dissemination of literary and artistic works using the various forms and methods, and the practical measures they took in the field of development of culture in the republic. The events, exhibitions, musical performances, views, competitions, festivals, fairs, the demonstration and promotion of works of theater and cinema conducted by the creative intellectuals represented in the various creative unions in the field of promotion of artistic culture and other actual issues were covered in detail. The great role of the creative unions in the cultural – educational work carried out in the republic, the practical activity that was visible in the promotion of works of art, the scope of the diverse work done by the creative intellectuals, the involvement of mass media in the promotion of art and the work done in this field, the participation of artists and professional creative intellectuals in the various meetings, round tables, discussions, disputes and creative hours, creative reports, etc. important issues have become the object of fundamental scientific – research works as a result of the intensive investigations of the researcher scientist Professor Nisbet Mehdiyeva, the scientific literature raised, the various sources, the archival materials, etc. [10, 12]. Professor Nisbet Mehdiyeva has investigated the forms and methods of work carried out by the creative unions in the republic in the field of mass propaganda, their innovative tendencies, progressive steps, new thoughts and ideas. The researcher correctly assessed the role of musical lecture halls, discussions of literary and artistic works, reader and audience conferences, disputes, direct communication with the wide audience of listeners, viewers, and readers, meetings, creative discussions, round tables, exchanges of ideas,

etc. in increasing the educational significance of literary and artistic works, and establishing the cultural – education work, and considered these areas of activity necessary in the field of development of culture [10, 18].

The poetry days, literary – artistic events, reader conferences, theoretical and creative conferences, creative disputes, etc., regularly held by the Azerbaijan Creative Unions in the various organizations, libraries, cultural palaces and clubs, ensured the continuous development of different spheres of culture [14, 22; 26, 17]. The researcher scientist, Professor Nisbet Mehdiyeva considers that the support and regular observance of the holding such conferences, creative debates and meetings by the creative unions were extremely necessary for the development of culture and the formation of a transparent, progressive atmosphere [18, 1, 2; 10, 19]. The audience conferences, creative meetings, meetings with the theater and cinema figures held by the Azerbaijan Theater Society and the Azerbaijan Cinematographers Union, the creation and activity of young playwrights, theater troupes, film crews, art clubs and the various departments under them – actors, theater critics, artistic design, etc. are reflected in the work of Professor Nisbet Mehdiyeva [10, 20, 22]. The researcher shows that it was necessary in this period to include in the research and study in detail the artistry shown by the Azerbaijan composers in connection with the development of various directions of folk, everyday music and professional music, the achievements gained in the process of conducting a truly creative intellectual struggle, and the existing shortcomings [27, 23; 10, 24 – 25]. The creative unions also used the various forms and methods, such as lectures – propaganda, reports, speeches, mobile plenums, conferences of different kinds, propaganda bureaus, creative trips, various creative events organized in clubs, cultural pal-

aces and cultural – educational institutions. The Exhibition halls, Art galleries, Composers` House, Cinema House, Actors` House, Art clubs, etc. organizations also played the great role in the effective implementation of cultural – educational work and cultural – aesthetic education of the people in the republic [10, 6]. During this period, the creative unions regularly fought for the ideological – political and aesthetic education of the population by the organizing events such as children`s and teenagers` literature days, poetry days, literature and art weeks, decades, artist days, theater days, culture days, visual arts week, “Open Door” days organized with art lovers in the workshops of prominent masters of brush – artists, theater weeks, folk theater weeks, cinema weeks, children and youth film weeks, music weeks, etc. Professor Nisbet Mehdiyeva showed these as the result of scientific investigations in her research work [10, 30 – 35; 16, 66]. The activity of the Azerbaijan Creative Unions in the field of cultural work in the various parts of the republic was also in the focus of attention of Professor Nisbet Mehdiyeva [10, 39; 15, 9]. The researcher rightly notes that the organization of cultural – educational institutions in the republic and the improvement of their activity are also included in the list of the main areas of activity of the creative unions.

In this regard, the Poetry houses, Literary posts, Ashug houses, Art galleries, etc. institutions organized by the Azerbaijan Creative Unions together with the Ministry of Culture and the Ashugs` Union of the Republic are the clear example of how wide the scope of activity of these organizations was in the 60 – 80s of the XX century [10, 45]. The creative unions considered the solution of problems facing the culture as the priority area of their activity, and played the decisive role in the formation and maturation of a person with high taste, broad worldview, comprehensively developed, mature, educated with the progressive thoughts and ideas, and familiar with the various problems of culture.

In 1991, the monograph of the researcher scientist, Professor Nisbet Mehdiyeva entitled “The cultural relations of the Azerbaijan Creative Unions” was published [12]. The relations of the Azerbaijan Writers` Union in the field of literary translation, the promotion of literature, literary – cultural events, the multifaceted relations of the Unions of Composers, Artists, Cinematographers, the Theater Society, and the “Azerbaijanfilm” studio of the Republic through the music, painting, theater and cinema works are reflected in the researcher`s monograph. The colorful spectrum and directions of these cultural relations carried out in cooperation with the relevant unions and organizations of the former Soviet republics and foreign countries have been investigated in detail here. The author`s mentioned monograph contains the certain proposals in the field of improving the forms and methods of the cultural relations of the Azerbaijan Creative Unions, increasing their efficiency, and putting forward some recommendations in connection with the elimination of the shortcomings made, which are quite relevant and should be considered the great achievement in the field of studying the cultural relations of the creative unions in the 60 – 80s of the XX century. The increase of the

role of culture in the development of society was one of the most important regularities in the 60 – 80s of the XX century. One of the most important elements ensuring the development of culture was the study of cultural relations and their involvement in scientific research. Under the influence of cultural relations, the development of national culture also contributed to the enrichment and progress of the people`s spiritual world. The Azerbaijan Creative Unions actively participated in the establishment, formation and development of the republic`s cultural relations. The forms and means of these relations were rich, their geographical scope was wide, and their importance was great. Professor Nisbet Mehdiyeva shows that the literary – cultural events such as the cultural relations, translation problems, discussions, conversations, etc., were widespread at the meetings held in the creative unions [12, 5]. The artistic intellectuals of the republic mobilized all their forces, demonstrating the position of intelligentsia in the field of developing the culture, establishing and strengthening the cultural relations, improving all areas of culture, and revealing their talent and craftsmanship [12, 6]. The forms and methods of relations of the Azerbaijan Creative Unions with the institutions and organizations engaged in the publication, demonstration and promotion of literary and artistic works of the various countries were quite diverse. The acquaintance, learning, establishing contacts, developing and enriching them, etc. took the important part in the activity of the creative unions. Professor Nisbet Mehdiyeva conducted the very large and valuable research work in the field of studying the cultural relations of the Azerbaijan Creative Unions.

The prominent researcher scientist Professor Nisbet Mehdiyeva published her second monograph in 2014. This monograph is called “The activity of the Azerbaijan Creative Unions in the field of the development of culture (1960 – 1980s)” [11]. This monograph of the Professor Nisbet Mehdiyeva reflects the issue of the activity of the Writers` Union, the Composers` Union, the Artists` Union, the Theatre Workers` Union and the Cinematographers` Union in the field of the development of culture in Azerbaijan historiography. The ideological – political level and professional mastery of the creative intellectuals in the republic, the creative and organizational work of the creative unions, their role in the promotion of artistic culture and their activity in the field of the cultural relations are discussed in detail in the monograph. The work of Professor Nisbet Mehdiyeva is a valuable object of research. The activity of the unions were quite extensive, significant and unique. The creative unions that united the talented creative intellectuals working in the various fields of art, created, developed and played the important role in the formation of artistic – aesthetic taste and raising the cultural level of people. Professor Nisbet Mehdiyeva, in addition to showing the achievements and successes gained in the process of explaining and developing each issue, also involved in the research the shortcomings made in detail. Such a global investigation of cultural problems requires great effort and labor from the researcher. While working on this topic, the author succeeded in writing a rather large and fundamental scientific research work in the field of applying theoretical

problems to practical activity, discovering a new way of understanding and truth, and involving the cultural problems in research from the different spectrum and various points of view. The prominent researcher, great scholar, who for many years conducted the significant researches in the field of culture, continuously worked in this area, relying on numerous facts and sources, focusing only on real events, scientific analysis, precise figures, true sources and scientific indicators, Professor Nisbet Mehdiyeva's scientific investigations in the field of culture in the republic have been invaluable, having the very significant impact on the development, formation, and enrichment of Azerbaijan culture, and the enormous scientific significance of this immense activity is undeniable.

Conclusion

Azerbaijan, which has gone through the great and very complex stage in its cultural development, has over time not only preserved its material and spiritual wealth, but also developed and enriched it, combined its creative directions and spectrums with the colorful and complex elements, and formed a new cultural meaning that is innovative, progressive, fighter, pure, honest and loyal to high ideals. The culture is also connected with the development of society and, incorporating all the manifestations, objective and subjective conditions, characteristic features, real and actual aspects of the period to which it belongs, becomes their real and honest embodiment. Thanks to the care of the state and the great love of the people, the various spheres of culture have turned from the general collective form into the areas of activity that operate independently, gradually develop, improve, enrich and constantly change, and at the same time remain faithful to all the laws of art.

The achievements in the field of culture in the republic during the 60 – 80s of the XX century were also directly connected in the effective and creative activity of the creative unions, which were already trying to speak their own words, directed their energies to the development of culture and united in their ranks the talented creative intellectuals. All components of culture were reflected in the activity of the creative unions.

The culture means the creativity. The creativity is manifested in the activity of the creative intellectuals. The creative intellectuals, distinguished by their skills and talents, endless desire to write and create, broad worldview, progressive thoughts and ideas, intellectual position, ability to describe the events only from the honest and realistic prism, and to bring real events and facts into art despite all the artistic imagination of the creative person, etc. superior qualities, were educated and developed as the intellectuals, and as they developed, they also developed, improved and modernized the culture. The creative intellectuals, working in the various fields of culture, created the remarkable dramas, demonstrated the beautiful acting, staged the interesting works and theatrical performances, created the films with rich plots, and sought solutions to the most difficult problems facing the culture by bringing them to art. They represented in the various creative unions, created the individual, unique, specific, thought – provoking and extremely valuable works of art. The ac-

tivity of these creative unions and their role in the development of culture were already being investigated by the research scientists, their scientific evaluation was given, precise scientific analysis was conducted, and research works were written.

The prominent research scientist, historian, Doctor of Historical Sciences, Professor Nisbet Mehdiyeva is the valuable scholar who, due to her work and extensive activity in the field of culture problems in the republic, the activity of the Azerbaijan Creative Unions in the field of mass propaganda, cultural relations, their development and strengthening, and the development of culture, covering the period of the 60 – 80s of the XX century, has made the enormous contributions to investigating the actual problems facing culture, dedicating and writing the fundamental scientific works to them. This talented researcher, Professor Nisbet Mehdiyeva, the skilled connoisseur and specialist in this field, who examined each sphere of culture, the obstacles and difficulties faced by these areas, the achievements and successes gained, step by step, has conducted very precise and detailed researches and scientific investigations, and has drawn up the accurate facts by referring to a large number of sources.

The significance of Professor Nisbet Mehdiyeva's scientific investigations in the field of culture, covering the period of the 1960s to the 1980s, is extremely great and valuable. The impact of these scientific researches on the development of Azerbaijan culture is invaluable and they are the valuable scientific resource.

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